

D 2.2 MECHANICAL FIELD EXTRACTION

enable

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Introduction

This report includes the progress made in the ENABLE project towards the development and implementation of a numerical tool able to be predict and simulate processes in which the material experiences severe loading conditions.

Given the need of enhancing the Classical Continuum Mechanics with features which would be able to explain the experimental evidence of moments rising in machining operations [Cahuc et al. 2010], following a literature survey, the decision to adopt a Cosserat description of the media was made. The Cosserat framework allows to include couple stresses in the continuum, which could be related to the application of external moments in the same way that external traction relates to internal stress .

The Cosserat model requires a calibration procedure with experimental results, and this report aims at individuating the elements which can be used to perform such calibration. In literature there are several works related to the constitutive model used in the Cosserat media both in plastic an elastic regime [Lakes 2016; Branke et al. 2010].

The report will follow with the the description of the most general Cosserat framework comprising kinematic, plasticity and thermodynamic aspects in part 1. The particular conditions in which this continuum model will be used are discussed, and the elements which require tuning from experimental results in these conditions will be highlighted. Following the analytical description, in the chapter 2 the Cosserat media will be employed and tested under small deformation assumption; a test benchmark able to highlight and differentiate the effects of the parameters of the Cosserat material model will be chosen. The influence of these parameters will be studied by mean of simulation of the same benchmark. Finally, these parameters will be extracted and an example of the calibration procedure will be given.

Chapter 1

Cosserat Media

1.1 Notations

Throughout this report zero, first, second, third and fourth order tensors are used in an Euclidean space. An Einstein notation is employed in the whole report if not otherwise stated. Tensors are indicated either through an indicial notation or, in a more compact way, as reported in Table 1.1:

Tensor Order	Levi-Civita Notation	Compact Notation
0	A	A
1	A_i	\underline{A}
2	A_{ij}	$\underline{\underline{A}}$
3	A_{ijk}	$\underline{\underline{\underline{A}}}$
4	A_{ijkl}	$\underline{\underline{\underline{\underline{A}}}}$

Table 1.1: Tensorial Representation.

Besides the standard algebraic operations defined on the first order tensors, the double contraction is introduced, and it is defined as follows:

$$\underline{\underline{A}} : \underline{\underline{B}} = A_{ijkl} B_{mnkl};$$

which can be performed on tensors whose order is larger or equal to 2.

Divergence and gradient operators are performed by mean of the Nabla operator ∇ . The gradient of scalars and first order tensors is indicated as:

$$\nabla A = A_{,i} \underline{e}_i; \quad \underline{A} \otimes \nabla = A_{i,j} \underline{e}_i \otimes \underline{e}_j;$$

where \underline{e}_i is the unit vector of the orthonormal basis $\{\underline{e}_1; \underline{e}_2; \underline{e}_3\}$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . The divergence of first and second order tensors reads:

$$\operatorname{div} \underline{A} = A_{i,i}; \quad \operatorname{div} \underline{\underline{A}} = A_{ij,j} \underline{e}_i;$$

At some point we will need to use the following operator:

$$\mathbf{a} = \text{axl}(\mathbf{A}) \Rightarrow a_i = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_{ijk}A_{jk}; \quad (1.1)$$

which returns the vector with the three only components of a skew-symmetric tensor. The term $\underline{\epsilon}$ is the Levi-Civita permutation symbol:

$$\epsilon_{ijk} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (i,j,k) = (1,2,3), (2,3,1) \text{ or } (3,1,2); \\ -1, & \text{if } (i,j,k) = (3,2,1), (2,1,3) \text{ or } (1,3,2); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

1.2 Elastic Cosserat

The Cosserat media, introduced in 1909 by the Cosserat brothers [E. Cosserat and F. Cosserat 1909], is an enhanced continuum mechanical model which belongs to the family of the Generalized Continuum Mechanics models. The Cosserat proposed an enhanced continuum with three additional degrees of freedom in the three-dimensional space:

$$\{u_i, \theta_i\}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1.2)$$

where u_i is the translational displacement of every point in the domain, and θ_i is the additional degree of freedom, which represents the independent rotation of a triad of directors attached to the microstructure. In small deformation, the following quantities are used to quantify the deformation of the continua:

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{u} \otimes \nabla + \underline{\epsilon} \cdot \boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = \boldsymbol{\theta} \otimes \nabla \quad (1.4)$$

Equation 1.3 indicates the Cosserat deformation tensor, while Equation 1.4 refers to the Cosserat wryness tensor. It might be here useful to expand the Cosserat strain and wryness tensor formulation to fully comprehend their structure:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e} = \frac{1}{2} & \begin{pmatrix} 2u_{1,1} & u_{1,2} + u_{2,1} & u_{1,3} + u_{3,1} \\ u_{2,1} + u_{1,2} & 2u_{2,2} & u_{2,3} + u_{3,2} \\ u_{3,1} + u_{1,3} & u_{3,2} + u_{2,3} & 2u_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & u_{1,2} - u_{2,1} & u_{1,3} - u_{3,1} \\ u_{2,1} - u_{1,2} & 0 & u_{2,3} - u_{3,2} \\ u_{3,1} - u_{1,3} & u_{3,2} - u_{2,3} & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\theta_3 & \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 & 0 & -\theta_1 \\ -\theta_2 & \theta_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_{1,1} & \theta_{1,2} & \theta_{1,3} \\ \theta_{2,1} & \theta_{2,2} & \theta_{2,3} \\ \theta_{3,1} & \theta_{3,2} & \theta_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

It can be observed that if the Cosserat rotation, *i.e.* θ_i , is equal to the material rotation, *i.e.* $0.5(\mathbf{u} \otimes \nabla)^{skew}$, the theory degenerates in the *Indeterminate Couple Stress Theory* [Eringen 1967; Toupin 1964]. The adjective indeterminate comes from the fact that the stress tensor and the couple stress tensor result to be partially undetermined under this constrain.

In order to define the theory, an elastic potential per unit mass must be defined, and it can be written in the following quadratic form:

$$\rho\Psi(\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e, \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e) = \frac{1}{2}\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Lambda}}} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + \frac{1}{2}\underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e + \frac{1}{2}\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \quad (1.7)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Lambda}}}$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}$ are their relative fourth orders elasticity tensors. The last term in the RHS of Equation 1.7 is a coupling term which vanishes under the assumption of point symmetry. From the potential defined in Equation 1.7, the stress and couple stress tensors can be respectively written as:

$$\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} = \rho \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Lambda}}} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e \quad (1.8)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} = \rho \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \quad (1.9)$$

in case of isotropic material, it could be demonstrated that the Cosserat stress and couple stress tensors assume the following forms:

$$\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} = \lambda \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} + 2\mu (\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e)^{sym} + 2\mu_c (\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e)^{skew} \quad (1.10)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} = \alpha \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{k}}^e) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} + 2\beta (\underline{\mathbf{k}}^e)^{sym} + 2\gamma (\underline{\mathbf{k}}^e)^{skew} \quad (1.11)$$

The stability condition expressed through the elastic coefficients reads:

$$\begin{cases} 3\lambda + 2\mu \geq 0 \\ \mu \geq 0 \\ \mu_c \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1.12)$$

$$\begin{cases} 3\alpha + 2\beta \geq 0 \\ \beta \geq 0 \\ \gamma \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1.13)$$

Unlike in the isotropic classical continuum model where two material parameters define the elastic response of the material, in the isotropic Cosserat media six parameters are required to describe its elastic behavior. From a simple dimensional analysis, an elastic characteristic length emerges from Equations 1.10 and 1.11. In fact, assuming that $\gamma = \beta$ the following can be found:

$$l_{el} = \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{\mu}} \quad (1.14)$$

It is important to remember that this characteristic length is not derived from any physical consideration.

Following Equation 1.10 it can be observed that the stress tensor is not symmetric as in the classical continuum mechanics.

By imposing that the external power is equal to the internal power, the equilibrium equations may be derived:

$$P^{(i)} = P^{(e)} \quad (1.15)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} p^{(i)} dV = \int_{\Omega} (\underline{\mathbf{f}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + \underline{\mathbf{c}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}}) dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} (\underline{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} + \underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \underline{\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}}) dS \quad (1.16)$$

where \mathbf{f} , \mathbf{c} , \mathbf{t} , \mathbf{m} are first order tensors indicating respectively the external body forces, the external body couples, the external surface traction and the external surface couple traction.

The internal power density is defined as:

$$p^{(i)} = \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}} + \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}} \quad (1.17)$$

By plugging Equation 1.17 into Equation 1.16 and reordering the result:

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}} + \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}} \right) dV = \int_{\Omega} \left(\mathbf{f} \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}}} + \mathbf{c} \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}}} \right) dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} \left(\mathbf{t} \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{u}}}} + \mathbf{m} \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}}} \right) dS \quad (1.18)$$

From which, the equilibrium equations can be written:

$$\text{div} \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} + \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{0} \quad (1.19)$$

$$\text{div} \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} + \text{axl}(\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}^{skew}) + \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0} \quad (1.20)$$

1.3 Elasto-Plasticity of the Cosserat Media

In a small deformation framework, the following additive decompositions hold:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}} = \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}}^e + \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}}^p \quad (1.21)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}} = \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^e + \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^p \quad (1.22)$$

The plastic evolution of the Cosserat media may be described by a single or a double plastic multiplier. In the former case, one only plastic multiplier exists both for plastic strain and plastic wryness, while in the latter case there exist two distinct plastic multiplier for strain and curvature:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}}^p = \dot{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}}, \quad \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^p = \dot{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}}}, \quad \text{or} \quad \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{e}}}}^p = \dot{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}}, \quad \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^p = \dot{k} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}}} \quad (1.23)$$

The yield function governing the plastic evolution of the Cosserat media can incorporate several behaviors such as isotropic hardening, kinematic hardening and so on. Assuming, for the sake of simplicity, only linear isotropic hardening to be present, the yield function can be expressed as:

$$f = f(\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}, \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}}, p) = \sigma_{eq} - Hp - \sigma_y \quad (1.24)$$

where H is the isotropic hardening modulus, σ_y is the initial yield stress and σ_{eq} is an equivalent measure of the local state of stress of the material. One method to express the equivalent stress in the Cosserat media is to extends a J-2 plasticity theory to a Cosserat continuum [Borst 1991; Lippmann 1969; Mühlhaus and Vardoulakis 1987], and it reads:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (a_1 \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}'}} : \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}'}} + a_2 \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}'}} : \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}'}}^T + b \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} : \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}})} \quad (1.25)$$

From this equation, assuming that $a_1 = a_2 = a$, another characteristic length can be identified, namely, the plastic Cosserat characteristic length:

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}; \quad (1.26)$$

A more complete formulation of the equivalent stress is given by the following [Forest and Sievert 2003]:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (a_1 \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}' : \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}' + a_2 \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}' : \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}'^T + b_1 \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} + b_2 \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^T)}; \quad (1.27)$$

This is a valid choice as well, as long as the quantities used to assess the equivalent stress state of the media do not vary with the frame of reference, *i.e.* they are invariant. However, it has been proven that due to the terms associated with the coefficients a_2 and b_2 in Equation 1.27, a miscoupling between in-plane and out-of-plane couple stresses in a 2D framework rises, therefore, in order to avoid this not-physical response, these coefficients are set as zero.

From the analysis of the invariants [Zheng 1994], a generic isotropic three-dimensional second order tensor, which can be decomposed in its symmetric and skew symmetric part, has the following invariants:

$$I_1(\underline{\mathbf{A}}) = \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{A}}^{sym}); \quad (1.28)$$

$$I_2(\underline{\mathbf{A}}) = \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{A}}^{sym2}) = A_{ij}^{sym} A_{ji}^{sym} = A_{ij}^{sym} A_{ij}^{sym}; \quad (1.29)$$

$$I_3(\underline{\mathbf{A}}) = \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{A}}^{sym3}); \quad (1.30)$$

$$I_4(\underline{\mathbf{A}}) = \text{trace}(\underline{\mathbf{A}}^{skew2}) = A_{ij}^{skew} A_{ji}^{skew}; \quad (1.31)$$

In case another quantity $\underline{\mathbf{A}}$ is used in the equivalent stress equation, it must be proved that it is invariant, that is, the following must hold:

$$f(\underline{\mathbf{A}}) = f(\underline{\mathbf{R}} \underline{\mathbf{A}} \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T); \quad (1.32)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{R}}$ is a rotation matrix. From Equation 1.24, assuming:

- Single plastic multiplier;
- Normality rule;
- Associated flow rule;
- Equivalent Stress as in Equation 1.27;
- Yield function as in Equation 1.24.

By imposing the following classical yield condition:

$$\begin{cases} f = 0 \\ \dot{f} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1.33)$$

The flow rules can be written as:

$$\dot{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}^p = \frac{3}{2} \dot{p} \frac{a_1 \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}' + a_2 \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}'^T}{\sigma_{eq}}; \quad (1.34)$$

$$\dot{\underline{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}}^p = \frac{3}{2} \dot{p} \frac{b_1 \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} + b_2 \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^T}{\sigma_{eq}}; \quad (1.35)$$

The estimation of the plastic multiplier can be performed:

$$\dot{p} = \frac{\frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}} : \dot{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\zeta}} : \dot{\underline{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}}}{\frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}} : \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\zeta}} : \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}}} + H}; \quad (1.36)$$

The evaluation of the plastic multiplier obviously depends on the form of the yield function, thus on the assumed plastic behavior of the media. A different plastic behavior would induce a different solution for the plastic multiplier. Furthermore, it is possible to evaluate the plastic multiplier in a closed form only if the yield conditions expressed in Equation 1.3 hold, that is, only if the plastic behavior is not viscous. In case a visco-plastic behavior must be defined, the same yield conditions do not apply and the evolution of the plastic multiplier is directly given.

1.4 Thermodynamically-Consistent Cosserat Media for Adiabatic Processes

The formulation of a thermodynamically-consistent theory of the Cosserat media for an adiabatic process requires the introduction and definition of several quantities in addition to the one described in sections 1.2, and 1.3, namely:

- The introduction of the additional Cosserat strain and Cosserat wryness due to temperature variation:

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{e}^e + \mathbf{e}^p + \mathbf{e}^{th}, \quad \mathbf{e}^{th} = (T - T_0) \mathbf{\Gamma} \quad (1.37)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{k}^e + \mathbf{k}^p + \mathbf{k}^{th}, \quad \mathbf{k}^{th} = (T - T_0) \mathbf{\Gamma}_k \quad (1.38)$$

- The definition of the set of state variables:

$$\{\mathbf{e}^e, \mathbf{k}^e, T, \alpha\} \quad (1.39)$$

- The introduction of the first Thermodynamic law:

$$\rho \dot{u} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\mathbf{e}} + \boldsymbol{\mu} : \dot{\mathbf{k}} - \text{div} \mathbf{q} + r; \quad (1.40)$$

- The introduction of the second Thermodynamic law:

$$\rho \dot{\eta} - \frac{r}{T} - \text{div} \left(\frac{\mathbf{q}}{T} \right) \geq 0; \quad (1.41)$$

- The definition of the Helmholtz free energy per unit mass:

$$\psi(\mathbf{e}^e, \mathbf{k}^e, T, \alpha) = u - T\eta; \quad (1.42)$$

- The linearized definition of the entropy per unit of mass as:

$$\eta = - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T}; \quad (1.43)$$

where \mathbf{e}^e , \mathbf{e}^p and \mathbf{e}^{th} are the elastic, plastic and thermal part of the Cosserat strain tensor, same classification holds for the Cosserat wryness tensor; T is the current temperature, and T_0 is a reference temperature; α is a parameter used to define the plastic evolution of the material, it can be a tensor or a scalar; ρ is the density of the material, u is the internal energy per unit mass, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux per current unit area, r is the heat internally produced per unit volume; finally, η is the entropy per unit mass. This set of equations are necessary to define the thermodynamic behavior of the Cosserat media. In this formulation,

the only feature which must be defined in order to characterize the material behavior is the Helmholtz free energy. The specific Helmholtz energy which has been chosen for this theory has the form of a quadratic potential and it is the following:

$$\rho\psi(\mathbf{e}^e, \mathbf{k}^e, T, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{e}^e : \underline{\underline{\Lambda}} : \mathbf{e}^e + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{k}^e : \underline{\underline{C}} : \mathbf{k}^e - (T - T_0)\underline{\underline{P}} : \mathbf{e}^e - (T - T_0)\underline{\underline{P}}_k : \mathbf{k}^e - \frac{1}{2}\rho\frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0}(T - T_0)^2 + \rho\psi_\alpha; \quad (1.44)$$

where $\underline{\underline{P}}$ and $\underline{\underline{P}}_k$ are the moduli expressing the magnitude of the stress produced as a response to a thermal variation, ψ_α represents the influence of the plastic behavior on the Helmholtz free energy and C_ε is the specif heat.

Clausius-Duhem inequality

Combining Equations 1.41 and 1.17 we can write the Clausius-Duhem inequality:

$$\rho(T\dot{\eta} - \dot{u}) + \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \dot{\mathbf{e}} + \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \dot{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{\mathbf{q} \cdot (\nabla T)}{T} \geq 0; \quad (1.45)$$

In order to obtain the constitutive Equations from the Clausius-Duhem inequality, the time variation of the Helmholtz free energy in its general formulation must be evaluated:

$$\dot{\psi} = \left[\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{e}^e} \dot{\mathbf{e}}^e + \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{k}^e} \dot{\mathbf{k}}^e + \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\alpha} \dot{\alpha} \right] = \dot{u} - T\dot{\eta} - \dot{T}\eta; \quad (1.46)$$

By plugging Equation 1.46 in 1.45, the latter can be rearranged as:

$$\left(\underline{\underline{\sigma}} - \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{e}^e} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{e}}^e + \left(\underline{\underline{\mu}} - \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{k}^e} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{k}}^e + \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : (\dot{\mathbf{e}}^p + \mathbf{e}^{th}) + \underline{\underline{\mu}} : (\dot{\mathbf{k}}^p + \mathbf{k}^{th}) - \rho \left(\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial T} - \eta \right) \dot{T} - \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\alpha} \dot{\alpha} + \frac{\mathbf{q} \cdot (\nabla T)}{T} \geq 0; \quad (1.47)$$

from which the constitutive laws can be derived:

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{e}^e}; \quad (1.48)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mu}} = \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{k}^e}; \quad (1.49)$$

The choice of the form of the Helmholtz free energy defines the type of elastic behavior of the material, in fact, from Equation 1.44, the linear-elastic material behavior laws can be written in their specific form as:

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{e}^e} = \underline{\underline{\Lambda}} : \mathbf{e}^e - \underline{\underline{P}}(T - T_0) = \underline{\underline{\Lambda}} : [\mathbf{e}^e - \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}^{-1} : \underline{\underline{P}}(T - T_0)] = \underline{\underline{\Lambda}} : [\mathbf{e}^e - \mathbf{e}^{th}]; \quad (1.50)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mu}} = \rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\mathbf{k}^e} = \underline{\underline{C}} : \mathbf{k}^e - \underline{\underline{P}}_k(T - T_0) = \underline{\underline{C}} : [\mathbf{k}^e - \underline{\underline{C}}^{-1} : \underline{\underline{P}}_k(T - T_0)] = \underline{\underline{C}} : [\mathbf{k}^e - \mathbf{k}^{th}]; \quad (1.51)$$

where:

$$\underline{\underline{\Lambda}}^{-1} : \underline{\underline{P}} = \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}; \quad (1.52)$$

$$\underline{\underline{C}}^{-1} : \underline{\underline{P}}_k = \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}_k; \quad (1.53)$$

Heat Equation

By plugging Equation 1.40 in 1.46, and considering Equations 1.43, 1.48 and 1.49 we obtain the *heat Equation* for the Cosserat continua:

$$\underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}} + \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}} + \text{div} \underline{q} + r = \rho \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e} \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e} \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} + \dot{T} \eta + T \dot{\eta} \right] \quad (1.54)$$

which, after simplification, becomes:

$$\underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^p + \underline{\sigma} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{th} + \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^p + \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^{th} + \text{div} \underline{q} + r = \rho \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} + T \dot{\eta} \right] \quad (1.55)$$

To explicitly describe the heat equation, the time variation of the entropy must be derived. From Equation 1.44, the entropy can be evaluated using Equation 1.43:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \eta = & -\frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e - \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{C}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e \\ & + \underline{\mathbf{P}} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e + \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \\ & + \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} (T - T_0) - \rho \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial T}; \end{aligned} \quad (1.56)$$

Successively, the variation of entropy with time can be evaluated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \dot{\eta} = & -\underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e - \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{C}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e - \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e - \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\boldsymbol{C}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \\ & + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e \\ & + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + \underline{\mathbf{P}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e + \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \\ & + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e + \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} \dot{T} \\ & + \rho \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} \frac{(T - T_0)}{T_0} \dot{T} - \rho \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T^2} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1.57)$$

where we considered the elastic moduli to be dependent on the temperature solely.

By adopting the Helmholtz free energy as defined in Equation 1.44, its time variation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \dot{\psi} = & \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \underline{\boldsymbol{C}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\boldsymbol{C}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e \\ & - \dot{T} \underline{\mathbf{P}} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e - \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e - (T - T_0) \underline{\mathbf{P}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e \\ & - \dot{T} \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e - \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e - (T - T_0) \underline{\mathbf{P}}_k : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e \\ & - \rho \dot{T} \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} (T - T_0) - \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} \frac{(T - T_0)^2}{T_0} \dot{T} \\ & + \rho \left(\frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{e}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{k}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \right); \end{aligned} \quad (1.58)$$

where the major symmetry of the elastic moduli has been used to simplify.

Flow Rules

In order to numerically solve the PDEs, we must provide the time derivative of the state variables to the solver. In this context, the time derivatives of the elastic Cosserat strain, elastic Cosserat wryness, temperature and hardening variables must be provided. The time variation of the elastic Cosserat strain and wryness can be evaluated considering that, from Equation 1.3 and 1.4, their are equal to:

$$\dot{\mathbf{e}}^e = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}} - \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{th} - \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^p = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}} - \dot{T} \underline{\underline{\Gamma}} - (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial T} \dot{T} - \dot{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\sigma}}}; \quad (1.59)$$

$$\dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}} - \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^{th} - \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^p = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}} - \dot{T} \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}_k - (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}_k}{\partial T} \dot{T} - \dot{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mu}}}; \quad (1.60)$$

where we assumed the normality rule to hold, an associated plastic potential and a single plastic multiplier for Cosserat strain and wryness. The plastic multiplier and the time variation of temperature must be evaluated.

We already discussed about how to obtain the former quantity, which, in case of linear isotropic hardening, its expression can be read in Expression 1.36 while the latter can be found by filling Equations 1.57 in 1.55:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^p + \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{th} + \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^p + \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^{th} + \text{div} \underline{\underline{q}} + r = \\ \rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} + T \left[- \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e - \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e - \dot{T} \frac{1}{2} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e \right. \\ \left. + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e \right. \\ \left. + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \dot{T} (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e \right. \\ \left. + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \dot{T} \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} \dot{T} \right. \\ \left. + \rho \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} \frac{(T - T_0)}{T_0} \dot{T} - \rho \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T^2} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \right) \right] \quad (1.61) \end{aligned}$$

from which, the variation of the temperature with time can be evaluated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{T} = & \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^p + \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^p + \text{div} \underline{\underline{q}} + r - \rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \\ & + T \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e - (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e \right. \\ & \left. - (T - T_0) \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \rho \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial \alpha} \dot{\alpha} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \\ & \left. \left(\begin{aligned} & - (T - T_0) \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial T} - \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \underline{\underline{\Gamma}} - (T - T_0) \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}_k}{\partial T} - \underline{\underline{\mu}} : \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}_k \\ & + T \left[- \frac{1}{2} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e - \frac{1}{2} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e : \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + 2 \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e \right. \\ & \left. + 2 \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + (T - T_0) \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T^2} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}_k}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e + \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} + \rho \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} \frac{(T - T_0)}{T_0} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T^2} \right] \end{aligned} \right)^{-1}; \quad (1.62) \end{aligned}$$

A series of assumptions can be made in order to obtain a simplified equation governing the thermodynamic of the Cosserat media.

1.4.1 From Generalized to Particular Model

Several combinations of assumptions can be made here, which depend on the type of phenomena analyzed. A list of possible hypothesis which can be made on the heat equations are listed:

- The elastic and thermal moduli are considered to be constant with the temperature, therefore their first and second derivatives with respect to the temperature are neglected:

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\Lambda}}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\Lambda}}{\partial T^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \underline{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial T^2} = 0; \quad (1.63)$$

- The Helmholtz free energy which depends on the state variable α is assumed to be dependent on α only, therefore:

$$\frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial T} = \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{e}^e} = \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \mathbf{k}^e} = 0; \quad (1.64)$$

- There is zero heat internal production and zero heat flux (adiabatic process):

$$\text{div} \mathbf{q} = r = 0; \quad (1.65)$$

- The specific heat C_ε is assumed to be constant with temperature:

$$\dot{C}_\varepsilon = 0; \quad (1.66)$$

- The moduli relating the stress/couples stress tensors with the temperature are assumed to be zero:

$$\underline{\Gamma} = \underline{\Gamma}_k = \underline{0}; \quad (1.67)$$

- The Helmholtz free energy is thought to be independent from the plastic-evolution parameter α :

$$\psi = \psi(\mathbf{e}^e; \mathbf{k}^e, T) \implies \psi_\alpha = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \alpha} = 0; \quad (1.68)$$

In case an extremely simplified model is required, the combination of all the previous assumption leads to the following heat equation:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \dot{\mathbf{e}}^p + \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \dot{\mathbf{k}}^p = T \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0} \dot{T}; \quad (1.69)$$

The increase in temperature due to plastic strain reads:

$$\dot{T} = \frac{T_0}{T \rho C_\varepsilon} \left(\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \dot{\mathbf{e}}^p + \underline{\boldsymbol{\mu}} : \dot{\mathbf{k}}^p \right); \quad (1.70)$$

This extremely oversimplified condition is the one that is commonly used to predict the increase in temperature due to plastic strain, corrected with a factor called the *Taylor-Quinney coefficient*. This value is included in the Equation to take into account the fact that not the whole dissipated plastic power induces thermal variation, *i.e.* to improve the prediction of the thermal variation due to the simplifications reported above. Although,

in simple cases, this extensive list of assumptions are representative of the conditions in which the simulation is performed, the processes in which we are interested (machining, friction steer welding, etc..) might diverge from them and the Equation 1.70 might result oversimplified. Given the generalized Equation 1.62, simplifications must be performed based on the foreseen conditions in which we would like to employ it. In order to simplify Equation 1.62 the order of magnitudes of the different terms have been explored and subsequent simplifications have been made. It was possible to do so by selecting the material which will be used and plastic behavior (ψ_α) which will be implemented. The choice of these two elements will allow us to evaluate the order of magnitudes of the terms in Equation 1.62 and to perform a simplification of the equation. A Johnson-Cook-based viscoplastic model and the Ti6Al4V were chosen.

Johnson-Cook-based visco-plastic model

The choice of the plastic model defines the term ψ_α in Equation 1.44 which is directly linked to the intrinsic dissipation potential of the media. Even though the aim of the project is to enhance the material characterization and avoid the adoption of the Johnson-Cook equation, a modified version of this famous plastic model is used here merely for descriptive purposes of the proposed multi-coupled approach. This is a convenient choice, because the Johnson-Cook plastic model includes both thermal and viscous effects and simulating their coupling is one of the aims of project. Since it is not trivial to derive a visco-plastic potential for the original Johnson-Cook model, a modified version is here used just for demonstration purposes, which still retains the same coupling between thermal and viscous effects:

$$\sigma_{JC} = [A + Bp^n] \left[1 + \left(\frac{\dot{p}}{\dot{p}_0} \right)^{1/k} \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^m \right]; \quad (1.71)$$

where A is the reference yield stress, B, k, n, m are coefficients which must be calibrated, p is the cumulative equivalent plastic strain, \dot{p}_0 is a reference plastic strain rate to be calibrated, T is the current temperature, T_0 is a reference temperature (often room temperature) and finally T_m is the material melting temperature.

This particular choice of the yield stress, is compatible with the definition of the following Norton-like visco-plastic potential:

$$\Omega = \frac{\dot{p}_0}{k+1} \sigma_{JC_0} \left(\frac{f}{\sigma_{JC_0}} \right)^{k+1}; \quad (1.72)$$

from which, considering the following:

$$\mathbf{e}^{\dot{v}p} = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{\sigma}}; \quad (1.73)$$

the time variation of the plastic multiplier can be defined as:

$$\dot{p} = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial f} = \dot{p}_0 \left(\frac{f}{\sigma_{JC_0}} \right)^k; \quad (1.74)$$

where the term $\mathbf{e}^{\dot{v}p}$ is the visco-plastic strain, which, in a viscous framework, takes the place of the plastic strain, and f is the following:

$$f = \sigma_{eq} - \sigma_{JC_0}; \quad (1.75)$$

the term σ_{JC_0} is the Johnson-Cook yield stress without the cumulative plastic strain rate contribution. Using the cumulative equivalent plastic strain as hardening parameter ($p = \alpha$), the component of the Helmholtz free energy associated with plasticity can be derived from:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \alpha} = \rho \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial p} = \sigma_{JC_0}; \quad (1.76)$$

from which:

$$\rho \psi_\alpha = \left[Ap + \frac{Bp^{n+1}}{n+1} \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^m \right]; \quad (1.77)$$

It can be noted that this contribution to the Helmholtz free energy is positive under the assumptions that the coefficient A and B are positive, that p is positive and that $T_0 < T < T_m$. In order to particularize the heat equation, the variation of Equation 1.77 with respect to temperature and equivalent plastic strain must be evaluated:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial T} = m \left[\frac{T_0}{(T_m - T_0)^2} \right] \left[Ap + \frac{Bp^{n+1}}{n+1} \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^{m-1} \right]; \quad (1.78)$$

from which:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T^2} = (m^2 - m) \left[\frac{T_0}{(T_m - T_0)^2} \right]^2 \left[Ap + \frac{Bp^{n+1}}{n+1} \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^{m-2} \right]; \quad (1.79)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial p} = m \left[\frac{T_0}{(T_m - T_0)^2} \right] [A + Bp^n] \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_0}{T_m - T_0} \right)^{m-1} \right]; \quad (1.80)$$

Equations 1.79 and 1.80 can be plugged in Equation 1.62 from which the thermo-plastic coupling results to be evident.

Titanium Alloy Ti-6Al-4V

Some further assumptions can also be done simply by defining the material behavior. Since the Project ENABLE focuses its attention on specific materials, one of the them was chosen: the Titanium Alloy **Ti-6Al-4V**. A quick dig into the literature allows us to simplify the equations above. In Figure 1.1 the mechanical parameters of the Ti-6Al-4V are reported [Handbook ASM International Committee 1990].

The Young modulus is characterized by a linear variation with the temperature, and the slope of the curve is approximately $6.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ GPa/°C. The Young modulus is assumed to be the only coefficient which varies with temperature in Equation 1.10 and μ_c is assumed to be constant with temperature. In first approximation, the thermal variation of the elastic moduli relating couple stress and Cosserat wryness is assumed to be null. The modulus coupling the couple stress and the thermal curvature ($\mathbf{\Gamma}_k$) is assumed to be zero due to the isotropic hypothesis. The variation of the coefficient of thermal expansion is also assumed to be linear in the thermal range [100-600°], and its slope is approximately $2 \cdot 10^{-8}$ /°C.

The first consequence coming from the choice of this material model is that the second derivative of the elastic moduli with respect to the temperature is null. The second consequence is that the terms related to the thermal variation of the elastic moduli in Equation 1.62 are negligible with respect to the term related to the plastic power.

An additional consideration can be made regarding the parameters \mathbf{P} : taking into account Equation 1.52 in fact, we can say that their order of magnitude is 10^5 /Pa/ °C. Again, taking into account Equation 1.52, the order of magnitude of the thermal variation of \mathbf{P} is 10^3 /Pa/ °C².

Figure 1.1: Variation of the mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4V with temperature. Young modulus (a), Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (b) [Handbook ASM International Committee 1990] and specific heat capacity [Boivineau et al. 2006].

Parameter	Order of Magnitude [Pa]
$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}^p$	10^9
$\underline{\underline{\mu}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^p$	10^9
$T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Lambda}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}^e$	10^7
$T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{k}}}^e : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{C}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{k}}}}^e$	10^7
$\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}^e$	10^3
$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} : \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}^e$	10^5
$T \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial T}$	10^4
$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}$	10^4
$T \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}}{\partial T} : \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^e$	10^3
$T \rho \frac{C_\varepsilon}{T_0}$	10^9
$T \rho \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} \frac{(T - T_0)}{T_0}$	10^8
$\rho \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial \alpha}$	10^9
$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T^2}$	10^{-1}
$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\alpha}{\partial T \partial p}$	10^{-1}

Table 1.2: Order of magnitudes of the terms in Equation 1.62.

The denominator in Equation 1.62 is dominated by the terms multiplying the density and the specific heat—or its thermal variation—and all the other terms are negligible. The variation of the specific heat capacity with the temperature of the Titanium Ti-6Al-4V has been provided by Boivineau et al. [Boivineau et al. 2006] and it is reported in Figure 1.1c. The steepness of the curve can be assumed to be approximately 0.25 J/Kg/°.

The only parameter missing is the cross-influence between the temperature and the part of the Helmholtz energy which accounts for hardening. The form of this contribution depends upon the definition of the plastic potential.

The orders of magnitude are reported in Table 1.2, where both the elastic strain and wryness are assumed to be in the orders of magnitude of 10^{-2} and $10^{-2}/\text{m}$ respectively, while their time variation in the orders of magnitude of 1/s and 1/m/s respectively. The temperature is assumed to be 500°C and the reference temperature to be 20°C.

Based on the analysis of the material data gathered in Table 1.2, the choice of neglecting all the terms whose order of magnitude is lower or equal to 10^7 has been made. This choice,

in addition to the analysis made on the modified Johnson-Cook plastic model described in Section 1.4.1, allows us to rewrite Equation 1.62 as:

$$\dot{T} = \frac{T_0 \left(\underline{\sigma} : \underline{\dot{\epsilon}}^p + \underline{\mu} : \underline{\dot{\kappa}}^p - \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial p} \dot{p} \right)}{\rho T \left[C_\varepsilon + \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} (T - T_0) \right]}; \quad (1.81)$$

It can be noted that in this case we do not require the adoption of any parameter to account for the simplifications that we made, since we quantified the influence of each term and neglected the ones which play a marginal role.

Chapter 2

Identifying Essential Mechanical Fields

In order to use the thermodynamically-consistent theory presented in the previous chapter, the parameters which define the thermo-mechanical behavior of the material must be extracted from experiments.

It is convenient to identify three different group of parameters, characterizing the linear-elastic, plastic and thermal aspect of the material behavior.

The parameters governing the linear-elastic response of a Cosserat material are observable in Equations 1.10 and 1.11, and they are:

$$\lambda; \quad \mu; \quad \mu_c; \quad \alpha; \quad \beta; \quad \gamma. \quad (2.1)$$

The constants λ and μ are the well known Lamé constants. Assuming $\gamma = \beta$ three parameters must be evaluated. Furthermore, in 2D, the parameter α is meaningless, and only two parameters must be evaluated. The first assumption physically means that both the symmetric and the skew-symmetric parts of the wryness tensor react with the couple stresses whose magnitude is the same. The second parameter (α), instead, relates the sum of the three torsional components of the wryness tensor with the couple stress. For example, the entry (1,1) of the couples stress tensor reads:

$$\mu_{1,1} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial \theta_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \theta_2}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \theta_3}{\partial z} \right) + \beta \frac{\partial \theta_1}{\partial x} \quad (2.2)$$

The plastic behavior of the Cosserat media, assuming as valid Expression 1.25, would require the calibration of 3 parameters:

$$a_1; \quad a_2; \quad b_1; \quad b_2. \quad (2.3)$$

As discusses in Section 1.3, we could arbitrarily decide to impose $a_2 = b_2 = 0$, and we are doing to do so, in order to avoid the mis-coupling presented before.

Besides these three parameters, shall the function describing the yield condition contain additional parameters, depending on its degree of complexity, also those require calibration, *e.g.* the parameters in the Johnson-Cook model.

The third set of parameters which require tuning are related to the thermal behavior of the material. The choice of the relevant parameters is strictly dependent on the degree of complexity required in the definition of Equation 1.61, thus on the type of assumption which will be made.

That said, the influence that an accurate estimation of the elastic parameters of Cosserat would have on the final result (in terms of accuracy of the prediction) is negligible in our case, since we are focusing on the application of this framework to processes where plasticity plays the major role. Nonetheless, the order of magnitude of these parameters must reflect experimental evidence and the choice must be reasonable. Ideally, the characteristic elastic length as defined in Equation 1.14 will be directly extracted from microscopic consideration purely physically based. Same holds for the influence of the thermal characterization of the media, whose influence on the total media behavior is not as important as the one that the plastic characterization has.

Overall, in order to calibrate the model, the fields which require to be extracted are:

- **Elastic strain distribution ;**
- **Temperature distribution;**
- **Plastic Strain distribution.**

However, as mentioned already, most of the attention will be focused on the plastic behavior of the material, rather than the thermal or elastic ones, due to the major role played by plasticity during manufacturing processes, meaning that most of the measured strain will be plastic. Therefore, gathering informations related to the total strain distribution would be enough to calibrate the model, and the Digital Image Correlation would be the most suitable test to do so. Due to the considerations done on the plastic Cosserat behavior, the most important and most relevant parameter which must be calibrated in this context is the **plastic characteristic length** given in Equation 1.26. This fundamental quantity, once calibrated, will be compared with the most interesting characteristic length of the micro-media, *i.e.* the average grain size.

Literature has been explored to choose a benchmark test which would be able to highlight the effect of the parameters which require calibration and subsequent extraction. The chosen test was a Hat-Shaped specimen under compression in a Split-Hopkinson bar, such that also the influence of high strain rate on the mechanical behavior could be assessed [Peirs et al. 2010]. A schematic representation of the specimen is given in Figure 2.1a, while the mesh structure and boundary conditions are reported in Figure 2.1b.

Thanks to the axial-symmetry, only half of the cross section needed to be modelled. The combination of specimen geometry and boundary conditions lead to shear localization and the appearance of a shear band.

In order to identify and evaluate the list of parameters which have been described so far, the benchmark which was chosen will be used. The calibration process will be driven by two main features which are extractable from the test: the **plastic distribution** in the shear band and the external **force-displacement** evolution. They will act as feedback to indicate the correctness of the choice of the parameters. Several tests will be performed, and the influence of these parameters will be studied and confronted to experimental results.

2.0.1 Cosserat Calibrating Example

In order to simulate the process of calibration, only for descriptive reasons, in this section we give an example of the procedure to follow. The Cosserat framework for large deformation still has to be developed, therefore a small deformation theory has been employed for the simulations. The reader should bare in mind that the results coming from the simulations reported here are not representative of the real test and this exercise is, once again, only

Figure 2.1: Hat-Shaped Specimen [Peirs et al. 2010]. Geometry (a) and Mesh with Boundary Conditions (b). Units in millimeters.

meant describe the calibration procedure which will be employed with the Cosserat large deformation framework. A small deformation theory has been used for the classical continuum mechanical model as well, so to make a conform calibration procedure.

It has been decided to use the modified Johnson-Cook law presented in the Subsection 1.4.1. With the purpose of describing a simple calibration procedure, it has been decided that the plastic component of the wryness is null, therefore it does not contribute to the equivalent stress measure, and the Cosserat wryness will be fully elastic. This choice has been made so that there is no influence of the plastic characteristic length in the model, and the elastic length now governs the Cosserat media behavior, thus becoming the most important parameter to be calibrated. Reminding Equation 1.14 and assuming $\beta = \gamma$, calibrating the elastic length means calibrating the parameter β .

The distribution of the equivalent plastic strain was used to calibrate the parameter. The result coming from the simulations in the classical continuum mechanical framework

Figure 2.2: Plastic distribution in a Hat-Shaped specimen in a Classical CM framework.

Figure 2.3: Plastic distribution in a Hat-Shaped specimen using the Cosserat framework with different values of β .

using the modified J-C behavior presented in Section 1.4.1 has been stored (Figure 2.2). Several simulations were performed (using different values of the elastic Cosserat length), from which the plastic strain distribution was analysed and compared to the benchmark case. The results extracted from the tests were taken at the same value of external applied displacement. The plastic distributions are reported in Figure 2.3. Due to the presence of a high stress concentration at the sharp angles, a large value of plastic strain was developed at that location (up to 6), therefore the colorscale has been manually set to span the values from 0 to 1 to neglect larger values and to focus on plastic distribution in the shear band.

It can be seen that the progression from a larger to a smaller value of $\beta = \gamma$ leads the solution of the plastic distribution towards the benchmark result, and that after a certain threshold an asymptotic behavior develops. The exact same distribution was not achieved due to the neglected influence of the couple stresses on the equivalent stress measure, which would have modified the average value of the equivalent cumulative plastic distribution. In case this element was not neglected, the calibration procedure would continue by choosing a small value of the β parameter and tuning the b parameter to obtain the same plastic distribution.

This small simplified example gives an idea on how the fields which will be extracted from the test will be used to calibrate the Large Deformation Viscoplastic Cosserat model.

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